

PRAGMATIC ASPECT OF TRANSLATION

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M.A.Tadjibayeva

*Vice principal of Presidential
school in Tashkent*

Annotation: *This article talks about the unique pragmatic feature of translation and the role of the field of pragmatics in translation. As we know, translation cannot represent a positive possibility without pragmatics. Any translation is inevitably linked to pragmatics.*

Any speech work, in addition to the linguistic material from which it is built, requires the presence of three more components as a necessary condition for its existence: *the topic of the message, the situation in which the communicative act is carried out, and the participants in this act*, who have both linguistic and extralinguistic knowledge. Accounting for non-linguistic moments is one of the necessary conditions for achieving translation adequacy, since in many cases the content of the text is revealed through them.

It is a known fact that the volume of these non-linguistic factors is not the same for different peoples, so the translator should not hope that the object described, for example, in the source text will be available to the representative of the target language, and therefore the translator must have all the necessary competencies to convey the content of the source text in a form understandable for the translation receptor. In linguistic literature, this moment is called the pragmatic aspect of translation. “The concept of pragmatics in linguistics (and, more broadly, in semiotics) is by no means reduced to the concept of pragmatic meanings of linguistic (and generally sign) units. This concept is much broader - it includes all issues related to the varying degree of understanding by the participants in the communicative process of certain linguistic units and speech works and their different interpretation

depending on the linguistic and non-linguistic (extralinguistic) experience of the people participating in communication " [Barkhudarov 2008: 107].

The pragmatics of translation is determined by V.N. Komissarov as "the influence on the course and result of the translation process of the need to reproduce the pragmatic potential of the original and the desire to provide the desired impact on the translation receptor" [Komissarov 1990: 210]. The pragmatic potential of the original is understood as "the ability of the text to produce a communicative effect, to cause the Receptor to have a pragmatic relationship to the reported, in other words, to exercise a pragmatic effect on the recipient of information" [Ibid.]. Based on the proposed by V.N. Komissarov's definitions, it is possible to identify the following chain of successive processes ending with a specific result: reproduction of the pragmatic potential of the source language → communicative effect on the recipient of the translated text → perception of the translation of the original message by the receptor.

Before proceeding with the translation, the translator needs to establish a number of essential points that contribute to the reproduction of the pragmatic potential of the original in order to achieve the task, i.e., to achieve the desired effect on the recipient of the translated text.

First, the translator must understand the communicative intention of the creator of the text, caused by some need.

Second, establish the dominant function of the text. Each text has a dominant function, the purpose of which is to have a certain pragmatic effect on the receptor of the text. This function is taken into account by the creator of the text when compiling it, for example, texts of a socio-political nature are intended to influence the public.

Thirdly, in the pragmatic aspects of translation, much attention is paid to the communicative orientation of the original message. A. Neubert identifies four types of texts, taking into account the fact that the involvement of pragmatic moments depends on the type of text being translated [Neubert 1978: 197-198].

1) Texts of a foreign policy and ideological nature, aimed at influencing the external public, i.e. citizens of other countries. Such texts are composed in such a way as to have a certain effect on a certain receptor. Taking into account pragmatic moments when translating such texts is necessary to achieve the desired effect.

2) Fiction works intended for native speakers of the source language, but in many cases they are translated into other languages, so pragmatic factors play an important role in them.

3) Texts that are of interest only to native speakers of the source language, for example, newspaper materials. Texts of this type are translated on a narrow scale, and therefore pragmatic points are not taken into account. However, when it is necessary to translate, for example, a newspaper article intended to be read by native speakers of the target language, one should take into account the pragmatics of the original.

4) Texts of a scientific and technical nature, created for scientific purposes and oriented both to native speakers of the source language and to native speakers of the target language involved in a particular scientific field. Here there is no need to pragmatically adapt the source text due to the fact that the speakers of the target language have the necessary information to understand and disclose the content of the text, since in this case there is no need for additional clarification.

And finally, in order to achieve the desired communicative effect, the translator has a number of techniques at his disposal to help him clarify those points of the source text that may not be understood by the translation receptor. These techniques constitute the so-called pragmatic adaptation of translation. Pragmatic adaptation is a change made to the text of the translation in order to achieve the necessary reaction from the translation receptor. About the changes that the translator makes in the translated text, A. Neubert writes the following “the duty of the translator to make such “changes” so that text B is obtained, which orients the recipient of the manual for the operation of the machine, speaking (the target language) in the same way as text A – speaking in (source language).

The result will be omissions, additions, permutations, shifts in emphasis, etc., which, if translated back verbatim, may seem to the speaker of (the original language) distortion, distortion, inadmissible addition, verbosity, omissions, a change in the usual classification "[Neubert 1978 : 195]. This multilevel analytical operation performed by the translator results in the translated text having the same pragmatic effect on its receptor as the source text had on its recipient. Here, however, the concept of "communicative effect" or "pragmatic impact" should be clarified. This is not limited to the concept of impact in the truest sense of the word, that is, to cause a specific reaction in the reader or make him experience some kind of emotion or feeling. It is wider, it also implies such a moment as the reader's understanding of the content of the message. This is precisely the task of the translator. This means that the translator must convey the content of the original so that the translation receptor understands the content of this text in the same way that the original receptor understands the original message. As for the concept of effect in the first sense, it is not always possible to achieve it. After all, even a text targeted at people belonging to the same society evokes a different reaction due to differences in the personal data of these people, not to mention people of a different culture, a different worldview. V.N. Komissarov rightly speaks about this fact: "the same reaction of the readers of the original and the translation is not an obligatory goal of any translation, and in some cases it is fundamentally unattainable, due to the peculiarities of the translation receptors, the inability to determine the reaction of the original receptors, and a number of other reasons" [Komissarov 1999: 140]. The reactions of the recipients of the source text and the translated text can only coincide if their personal characteristics are the same, "if we compare the fan of all possible individual reactions to the source text and the same fan of reactions to the translated text, then those individual reactions will coincide where the individual-personal characteristics of the addressees of the source text and the translated text. This means that the archetypes of reactions of individuals, classes of reactions to the source text and to the translated text coincide. In this sense, the equivalence of the regulatory impact of the

source text and the translated text means literally the following: the source text and the translated text give their addressees an objective opportunity to respond to the message in the same way, and whether the reactions of multilingual addressees will be equivalent depends on the degree of coincidence of their individual-personal properties" [Latyshev 2008: 32]. Since the translation is intended for another person who has a different mentality, belongs to a different society, it is necessary to adapt the original text so that it is accessible to him. Adaptation is carried out with the help of extralinguistic information of the translator. There are some ways to adapt the original text, such as: 1) adding; 2) omission; 3) generalization; 4) concretization; 5) comments.

As an example of the use of the addition, we give the following sentence: *"It is impossible to imagine Russia without the Volga"*. Any Russian reader knows what the Volga is, but this information is not supposed to be known to the Uzbek reader, and therefore the word "river" must be added to the translated text.

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